

Social Media Usage and Academic Performance of Grade 6 Pupils

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ABSTRACT

This quantitative, descriptive-correlational study examined the relationship between social media usage and academic performance among 30 Grade 6 pupils at an elementary school, Banga, Aklan, Philippines. The primary objective was to determine how the extent of use and social media engagement relates to the academic performance outcomes within local elementary setting. Data were gathered using a 15-item researcher-made questionnaire, which assessed three dimensions of usage: time spent and frequency of use, impacts on the study habits and potential distractions, and if the platforms were used for learning and school related tasks. Academic performance was quantified using the pupils' General Weighted Average (GWA) from the most recent term. Statistical

analysis revealed that there was a weak negative relationship between social media usage and academic performance, the correlation was not strong enough to imply a direct casual effect. Results also shown that the pupils had moderate level of social media usage and a generally satisfactory academic performance. The study acknowledges limitations: due to the small sample size drawn from only one school restricts the generalizability to other grade levels or districts. The results therefore warrant cautious interpretation and replication with larger, paired-data studies.

Keywords: *Academic Performance, Grade 6 Pupils, Social Media Usage, Social Networking Sites, Study Habits*

INTRODUCTION

Social media has become an essential part of our daily lives, revolutionizing the way we work, communicate and live. Across different generations - both adults or youth, social media serves as a versatile tool through various platforms, offering entertainment or practical value. Even schools had already adapted the use of social media generally because they are useful when it comes to sharing information or organizing tasks.

According to Samala et al. 2024, social media features such as posting and interactive discussion through social media builds a strong engagement between teacher and students. Results from the study of Omar & Ondimu, 2024, It enhances student collaboration, it has easy access to resources and it supports innovative teaching methods. However, it also addresses the potential distractions, cyberbullying, and academic dishonesty associated with social media use, emphasizing the need for digital literacy and ethical usage in educational settings. Concerns about problematic use are grounded in addiction frameworks that explain how excessive engagement can displace study time and self-regulation (Kuss & Griffiths, 2017), and excessive or unregulated use often displaces time intended for school work, leading to procrastination

and poor study habits-linking to lower academic performance (Aragon et. Al., 2023). Beyond time management, heavy social media engagement is associated with poorer psychological functioning, including increased anxiety and emotional distress; these mental states act as indirect barriers that reduce focus and motivation, ultimately affecting classroom performance (Mougharbel et al., 2023). Furthermore, excessive use often disrupts sleep quality, which further impairs cognitive function and academic outcomes (Salari et al., 2025). Findings remain mixed: some studies report negative associations between social media use and grades, while others find no significant relationship — outcomes depend largely on whether use is recreational or educational, how it is measured, and the age and context of the learners. Thus, whether social media brings benefit or harm it depends on how the students use it: intentional, purposeful use may lead to positive outcomes such as engagement and enjoyment, while excessive or compulsive use can contribute to negative effects like stress, anxiety, and low mood (Chen & Xiao, 2022). Strategic use can support learning, uncontrolled, entertainment-focused usage is more often linked to academic challenges (Dimalna & Sambo, 2025). Despite this growing body of work, most studies focus on older students or urban settings. There is limited research specifically examining Grade 6 learners in local Philippine communities, where access and usage patterns may differ. Therefore, this study aims to determine the relationship between social media usage patterns and the academic performance of Grade 6 pupils at an elementary school in Banga, Aklan, Philippines.

METHODS

Research Design

The study utilized a quantitative, descriptive-correlational research design to determine the effects of social media usage on the academic performance of Grade 6 pupils. Quantitative research focuses on gathering numerical data and analyzing it using statistical methods to identify relationships, trends, and patterns. This design was considered appropriate because the study aimed to measure the level of social media usage and examine its relationship with pupils' academic performance through objective and measurable data.

The descriptive aspect describes the level of social media usage in terms of time and frequency, study habits and distractions, and educational use as well as the pupil's level of academic performance. The correlational aspect determines whether there is a significant association between the two variables without implying cause-and-effect.

This research design was appropriate because it allowed the researchers to gather factual information and determine the degree of relationship between variables without altering the natural learning environment of the respondents.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at a public elementary school located in Banga, Aklan, Philippines. The school operates under the Department of Education (DepEd) and serves learners from the local community.

The locale was selected because it reflects a typical public elementary school setting where pupils have increasing access to smartphones, internet connectivity, and social media platforms. The growing use of digital technology among elementary pupils in rural and semi-rural communities made the school an appropriate setting for investigating the effects of social media on academic performance.

Furthermore, the accessibility of the respondents and the cooperation of school administrators and teachers contributed to the suitability of the locale for the study.

Sampling Technique

The respondents of the study were the 30 Grade 6 pupils of an elementary school in Banga, Aklan, Philippines. Since the population was small, the researchers used total enumeration or census sampling,

where all members of the population were included in the study. This sampling technique ensured complete representation of all Grade 6 pupils and minimized sampling bias.

The respondents included both male and female pupils officially enrolled during the current school year. To ensure ethical considerations, only pupils whose parents or guardians provided consent were allowed to participate in the study. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were informed that their answers would remain confidential and used solely for academic purposes.

The researchers considered the total population sufficient for conducting descriptive and correlational analysis because it represented the entire Grade 6 class of the school.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before conducting the study, the researchers first secured permission from the school principal. After approval was granted, parental consent letters were distributed to the parents or guardians of the Grade 6 pupils to ensure ethical compliance and voluntary participation.

Upon receiving the signed consent forms, the researchers coordinated with the class adviser regarding the schedule for administering the questionnaire. The survey was conducted during class hours under teacher supervision to ensure proper guidance and orderly administration.

The respondents were given sufficient time, approximately 20 to 30 minutes, to answer the questionnaire. The researchers explained the purpose of the study and assured the respondents that their answers would remain confidential and anonymous.

After the questionnaires were collected, the researchers requested the respondents' General Weighted Averages (GWA) from the class adviser with approval from the school principal. All gathered data were organized, tabulated, and prepared for statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

The study employed various descriptive statistics (mean, frequency, standard deviation, and percentage), and Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient. Mean and standard deviation were used to categorize the levels of social media usage. Since social media usage and academic performance was both represented by nominal data, Spearman's correlation is used to measure the strength and direction of association between the two variables.

Data analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 21) to ensure its accuracy and reliability.

The academic performance of grade 6 pupils is classified based on DepEd's grading scale and its descriptive equivalents. (DepEd Order 8, series of 2015)

Numerical Value	Description
90-100	Outstanding
85-89	Very Satisfactory
80-84	Satisfactory
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory

According to the guidelines of Akoglu (2018), correlation coefficients were categorized as follows:

Correlation Coefficient	Verbal Interpretation
±1	Perfect Correlation
±0.7 - ±0.9	Strong Correlation
±0.4 - ±0.6	Moderate Correlation
±0.1 - ±0.3	Weak Correlation
0	No Correlation

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Devices and Social Media Networks Used by Respondents

The data reveals that out of 30 grade 6 pupils, 28 or 93.33% uses mobile phones, indicating that it is the primary device for accessing social media. Only few of them uses tablet/iPad (2 pupils, 6.67%) and laptops/computers (4 pupils, 13.33%). Because the questionnaire used a “check all that apply” format, these counts are not mutually exclusive (students could report more than one device), but the large gap between smartphone use and other devices clearly shows smartphones dominate device access.

Table 1. *Devices used by Grade 6 Respondents*

Device	No. of Students	Percentage
Smartphone/Cellphone	28	93.33%
Tablet/iPad	2	6.67%
Laptop/Computer	4	13.33%

Note: The questionnaire used a "check all that apply" format, allowing respondents to mark all applicable choices.

Additionally, the results reveal that TikTok is the most widely used social media platform among the Grade 6 pupils, with 76.67% (n = 23) of respondents indicating that they use the platform. This is followed by Facebook (n = 19, 63.33%), YouTube (n = 16, 53.33%), Messenger (n = 15, 50.00%), and other platforms (n = 12, 40%). Meanwhile, Instagram recorded the lowest usage rate at 20.00% (n = 6). The findings suggest that pupils are more inclined toward platforms that provide short-form video content and entertainment, particularly TikTok. The popularity of TikTok among the respondents may indicate its strong influence on their online activities and media consumption patterns.

Table 2. *Social Media Networks used by Grade 6 Respondents*

Device	No. of Students	Percentage
TikTok	23	76.67%
Facebook	19	63.33%
YouTube	16	53.33%
Messenger	15	50%
Other Platforms	12	40%
Instagram	6	20%

Note: The questionnaire used a "check all that apply" format, allowing respondents to mark all applicable choices.

Levels of Social Media Usage

A. Time and Frequency of Use

Table 3 shows that Grade 6 respondents use social media at a moderate level, with an overall mean of 3.25 (Sometimes). The highest-rated indicators were spending more than 2 hours per day scrolling (\bar{x} = 3.60) and using social media more on weekends (\bar{x} = 3.60), both interpreted as “Often”. Meanwhile, using social media immediately after waking up, during class breaks, and staying up late to watch or chat were rated “Sometimes”, indicating that these behaviors occur occasionally but are not consistently practiced by most respondents.

Table 3. *Social Media Usage of Grade 6 Respondents in Terms of Time and Frequency*

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
A1. Use social media as soon as I wake up	3.10	1.30	Sometimes
A2. Spend >2 hours/day scrolling	3.60	1.33	Often
A3. Use social media during class breaks	2.87	1.26	Sometimes
A4. Stay up late to watch/chat	3.10	1.37	Sometimes

A5. Use social media more on weekends	3.60	1.36	Often
TOTAL	3.25	4.06	Sometimes

Note: Description is based on the following scale: 0-1.4 (Never), 1.5-2.4 (Rarely), 2.5-3.4(Sometimes), 3.5-4.4 (Often), 4.5-5 (Always)

B. Study Habits and Distractions

Table 4 indicates that social media sometimes affects the study habits and attention of Grade 6 respondents, with an overall mean of 2.93 (Sometimes). The highest mean was losing focus because of notifications ($\bar{x} = 3.13$), followed by using social media while doing assignments ($\bar{x} = 3.10$). The lowest mean was skipping important topics to spend time on social media ($\bar{x} = 2.57$).

These findings suggest that social media can be a source of distraction, but its impact on academic activities is generally moderate rather than frequent.

Table 4. *Social Media Usage of Grade 6 Respondents in Terms of Study Habits and Distractions*

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
B1. Check social media before homework	2.83	1.55	Sometimes
B2. Use social media while doing assignments	3.10	1.42	Sometimes
B3. Lose focus because of notifications	3.13	1.23	Sometimes
B4. Spend time on social media rather than reading	3.03	1.35	Sometimes
B5. Skip studying important topics to spend time on social media	2.57	1.20	Sometimes
TOTAL	2.93	4.30	Sometimes

Note: Description is based on the following scale: 0-1.4 (Never), 1.5-2.4 (Rarely), 2.5-3.4(Sometimes), 3.5-4.4 (Often), 4.5-5 (Always)

C. Educational Use

Table 5 presents the extent to which Grade 6 pupils use social media for learning and school-related purposes. The overall weighted mean of 3.85, interpreted as Often, indicates that pupils frequently utilize social media as a tool to support their studies. Among the indicators, the highest mean scores were obtained by using social media to find educational resources ($\bar{x} = 4.13$), using Messenger to ask classmates or teachers about school-related concerns ($\bar{x} = 4.10$), and learning new study techniques through social media ($\bar{x} = 4.10$), all of which were described as Often.

These findings suggest that pupils commonly use social media platforms to access learning materials, communicate with peers and teachers, and discover effective study strategies. Additionally, watching educational videos on YouTube or TikTok obtained a mean score of 3.57, also interpreted as Often, indicating that pupils frequently engage with educational content online. On the other hand, sharing helpful school materials with others received the lowest mean score of 3.37, interpreted as Sometimes, suggesting that this practice is less common compared to the other activities.

Overall, the results reveal that although pupils use social media for entertainment, they also actively take advantage of its features to support their academic learning and school-related needs.

Table 5. *Social Media Usage of Grade 6 Respondents in Terms of Educational Use*

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
C1. Use Messenger to ask classmates/teachers	4.10	1.30	Often
C2. Watch educational videos on YT/TikTok	3.57	1.20	Often
C3. Learned new study techniques via social media	4.10	1.08	Often
C4. Use social media to find educational resources	4.13	0.88	Often
C5. Share helpful school materials	3.37	1.40	Sometimes

TOTAL **3.85** **3.65** **Often**

Note: Description is based on the following scale: 0-1.4 (Never), 1.5-2.4 (Rarely), 2.5-3.4 (Sometimes), 3.5-4.4 (Often), 4.5-5 (Always)

Level of Academic Performance

Table 6 presents the level of academic performance of the Grade 6 pupils based on the Department of Education (DepEd) grading scale. Out of the 30 respondents, the largest proportion of pupils (36.67%, $n = 11$) attained a Very Satisfactory rating (85–89). This was followed by pupils who achieved an Outstanding rating (90–100), comprising 26.67% ($n = 8$) of the respondents. Meanwhile, 23.33% ($n = 7$) obtained a Fairly Satisfactory rating (75–79), while the smallest group, 13.33% ($n = 4$), achieved a Satisfactory rating (80–84).

Overall, the results indicate that a majority of the pupils (63.34%) performed at the Very Satisfactory and Outstanding levels, suggesting generally favorable academic performance among the respondents. These findings provide an important basis for examining the influence of social media usage on academic performance. Since most pupils demonstrated relatively high academic achievement, the study may further explore whether their patterns of social media use contribute positively, negatively, or have no significant effect on their academic outcomes. The distribution of performance levels presented in this table serves as a foundation for analyzing the relationship between social media usage and the academic achievement of Grade 6 pupils.

Table 6. *Level of Academic Performance of Grade 6 Pupils*

Classification	n	Percentage
Outstanding (90–100)	8	26.67%
Very Satisfactory (85–89)	11	36.67%
Satisfactory (80–84)	4	13.33%
Fairly Satisfactory (75–79)	7	23.33%
TOTAL	30	100%

Note: Classification is based on DepEd's grading scale and its descriptive equivalents (DepEd Order 8, Series of 2015)

Social Media Usage to Level of Academic Performance

Table 7 presents the relationship between the level of social media usage and the academic performance of Grade 6 respondents. The results show a Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (r_s) of 0.154, indicating a very weak positive correlation between social media usage and academic performance. This suggests that as social media usage increases, academic performance tends to increase slightly; however, the relationship is minimal.

Furthermore, the computed p-value of 0.416 is greater than the level of significance of 0.05 ($p > 0.05$). This indicates that the observed relationship is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between social media usage and academic performance is accepted.

The findings imply that the level of social media usage among the Grade 6 respondents does not have a significant influence on their academic performance. Despite the generally high academic performance observed in Table 6, the results suggest that differences in social media usage are not associated with significant differences in pupils' academic achievement. This may indicate that other factors, such as study habits, parental supervision, learning environment, motivation, and access to educational resources, play a more substantial role in determining academic performance than social media usage alone.

Overall, the study concludes that social media usage is not significantly related to the academic performance of Grade 6 pupils, as evidenced by the weak correlation and non-significant p-value. These

findings suggest that social media use, by itself, may not be a determining factor in the academic success of the respondents.

Table 7. *The Relationship Between the Level Social Media Usage and Level of Academic Performance of Grade 6 Respondents*

	r_s	p-value	Interpretation
Social Media Usage * Academic Performance	0.154	0.416	<i>no significant relationship</i>

No significant relationship at $p > 0.05$.

CONCLUSION

The study found that Grade 6 pupils primarily access social media through mobile phones, with TikTok being the most commonly used platform. The respondents demonstrated a moderate level of social media usage, with social media occasionally affecting their study habits and attention. However, the findings also showed that pupils frequently use social media for educational purposes, such as accessing learning materials, communicating with classmates and teachers, and watching educational content.

In terms of academic performance, most respondents achieved Very Satisfactory and Outstanding ratings, indicating generally high academic achievement. Furthermore, the correlation analysis revealed a very weak positive relationship between social media usage and academic performance ($r_s = 0.154$), which was not statistically significant ($p = 0.416$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Based on the findings, it is concluded that social media usage has no significant relationship with the academic performance of Grade 6 pupils. While social media may serve as both a source of distraction and a tool for learning, it does not appear to be a determining factor in pupils' academic achievement.

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